

PROCESSES OF BENEFICIATION AND EXTRACTION OF ORES IN IRON MINES (IN THE EXAMPLE OF TEBIN BULAK IRON MINE)

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7620881>

Abstract: Considering the continuous decrease of titanium, rutile and ilmenite mineral deposits, There are cost-effective ways to produce titanium using vanadium titanomagnetite as a raw material, becomes more and more important. In this study, vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate was obtained. Magnetic separation for downstream production at the Tebin Bulak metal ore mine in Uzbekistan processes such as high quality vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate are featured. Otelbayev Azizbek Tebin, a student of the Nukus Mining Institute at the Navoi State University of Mining and Technologies, saw the processes at the Bulak mine. 521 detonators were detonated in the first blasting. This was a potential use of the concentrate checked. Mineral separation analysis and electron microprobe analysis were used for the research deporting impurities and basic minerals. Experimental results showed that magnetic separation. Compared to the raw concentrate, the level of Fe in the Tebin Bulak deposit is 16%-33%, while Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgO , and CaO impurities decreased from 15.35% to 6.47%. Process mineralogy studies confirmed this the proportion of titanomagnetite increased in high-quality vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate up to 95.84%. Spinel and sphene were embedded in nanometer-scale titanomagnetite particles, This makes it almost impossible to remove them through mineral processing methods.

Key words: Iron ore beneficiation, vanadium titanomagnetite, fine grinding, concentration, magnetic separation, process mineralogy, blasting processes, rock crushing processes

Introduction

Employees of the Nukus Mining Institute of the Navoi State University of Mining and Technology at the Tebin spring mine DJaksimuratov.K., Otelbayev.A., Jumabayeva.G. Witnessed the first blasting of the mine. The Tebinbulok mine, the largest iron ore mine in Uzbekistan, can be considered the most important source of raw materials for the country's metallurgical industry. Projected

reserves of P1 grade ore are 450 million tons, with an average grade of 16.2% iron and 0.15% vanadium pentoxide. P2 ore reserves are 550 million tons. In total, the amount of titanomagnetite ores is estimated at 4.5 billion tons for the entire deposit and 2.0 billion tons for the West Zone. Appropriate favorable conditions should be considered: open work, proximity to rail and road transport, oil and water pipelines and high-voltage power lines, and the availability of a large labor pool. According to the composition of minerals in iron, ores can be divided into massive, coarsely absorbed and absorbed. It appears that all ores are complex and contain vanadium. There are two main methods of processing vanadium titanomagnetites - hydrometallurgical and pyrometallurgical. The implementation of the pyrometallurgical technology of Tebinbulak titanomagnetite processing allows partial or complete abandonment of scrap metal, providing the Republic of Uzbekistan with the necessary steel, and leaving the excess steel for export to neighboring countries. Work on the implementation of the above technology may begin in the near future. For this to happen, three conditions must be met: the mine must be found to contain iron-rich ore; equipment for metallization of iron ore must be available (existing furnaces can be used for this purpose after modification); The electric steel foundry at the Metallurgical Plant of Uzbekistan (in the city of Bekobod) should be able to convert the metallized product into natural alloy steel. Milling in a closed circuit with hydrocyclones and stone crushing - rough magnetic separation - stone milling - clean magnetic separation. Ore-coal pellets can be obtained using any non-coking coal, with a sulfur content limited to 0.3%. Pellets are metallized in grid-type units with a solid reducing agent at temperatures in the range of 1500-1500 °C. Heat is provided by burning natural gas. Metallized pellets obtained at such high temperatures are non-pyrophoric and can be transported over long distances. Pellets are melted in conventional steelmaking furnaces (electric furnaces) to obtain standard metal, including alloy steels. The conducted tests included the processing of high-grade Tebinbulok ore in the main arc furnaces at the Metallurgical Combine of Uzbekistan together with the Institute of Metallurgy. Tests have shown that good results can be achieved in the processing of this raw material, the final product is high-quality vanadium-microalloy (0.011-0.052%) steel. Economic calculations were conducted several times to assess the feasibility of developing the Tebinbulok mine for commercial purposes. Calculations confirmed the feasibility of building a mining-metallurgical complex producing vanadium metallized granules and a wide range of structural materials. Calculations were also carried out on the "turnkey"

version of the complex, it was assumed that the ore would contain 15%-33% iron, and it was necessary to concentrate it before metallization. Capital costs for project implementation can be reduced by applying the following measures:

-> The metallized product could be obtained from massive titanomagnetite ores, which initially contained more than 30% iron and could be processed without additional concentration; money from the sale of this product can then be used to build facilities for the production of concentrate from low-grade ores;

-> The metallized product could be obtained not only in expensive shaft furnaces and in modules designed for solid-phase reduction of ferro-coal.

However, there should be an alkaline stream is added directly to the raw material during the reduction process improving separation between iron and slag. It is indirect reduces the titanium level of the raw material. As a result, the smelting slag contained 30-33% TiO_2 . recovery of titanium from slag smelting by hydrometallurgy or due to pyrometallurgy methods are very difficult amount of impurities and complex mineralogical characteristics. This type of titanitic slag (containing 30-33% TiO_2) also exists collected as solid waste. Hence, effectively extracting titanium from titanium electric furnace slag has become a significant problem. Research TiO showed when Titanium slag has 2 components Above 35%, it can be recovered by acid washing methods. Therefore, improving the level of TiO_2 in titanium slag, the reduction-smelting process was followed by Iron and steel group. Vanadium depletion in this process titanomagnetite concentrate (contains about 40% Fe) conducted in a rotary kiln or rotary hearth furnace, then metallized pellets were melted in an electric arc furnace lack of flow environment. The product is titanium slag Contains 20-35% TiO . However, the composition of impurities, especially the content of SiO_2 , was still high, making it very difficult to extract TiO_2 from the slag due to the low acidolysis of the slag. So it is very important reduce these impurities during the pretreatment stage obtaining the desired titanium slag ($TiO_2 > 50\%$) and Further extraction of TiO_2 is possible and efficient. However, There is minimal information on preparation Titanium slag with high TiO_2 content and preparation titanium white by processing titanium slag with sulfur acid. Effective problem solving is essential exploiting the available titanium resource in vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate due to large reserves of Vanadium titanomagnetite in an iron deposit. Unfortunately, only a few studies have been conducted on the use of titanium slag from vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate Iron ore mainly due to complex phase composition and high content of impurities such as SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , MgO and CaO . Reduction of impurities in vanadium titanomagnetite

Concentration to improve the mass ratio of TiO_2 to impurities a an effective strategy to obtain high-quality titanium slag through redox process.

Impact forces in magnetic extraction of iron ores

Since the Fe level of the concentrate after one treatment low, secondary cleaning was performed on the lower magnet intensity. The magnetic field intensity used for the secondary The effect of cleaning was 300-850 Gs of Fe level and magnetic field intensity on Fe recovery shows a high quality concentrate after secondary treatment The level of Fe increased magnetically field intensity decreased. However, the decrease in the magnetic field Intensities below 628 Gs resulted in a slight improvement The level of Fe, and the regeneration of Fe, decreased dramatically. That is why, A magnetic field intensity of 628 Gs is recommended. The chemical composition of the obtained high-quality concentrate are presented in Table II. The level of Fe reached 53.24% with TiO_2 composition 14.15%. The regeneration of Fe and TiO High-quality concentrates from 2 were 82.28% and 81.35%, respectively. Total amount of SiO_2 , mixtures of Al_2O_3 , MgO and CaO . It decreased from 13.35% to 8.73%. mass ratio of $TiO_2/(TiO_2+SiO_2+Al_2O_3+CaO+MgO)$ increased to 0.633, which showed this is TiO Theoretically, titanium slag can have 2 compositions in its absence reaches about 63% after reduction-dissolution from the addition. Even after adjusting the binary cardinality to 0.61-1.0, The composition of TiO_2 can remain above 55% in slag. Shown by using high quality vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate during reduction-melting process; TiO The content of 2 in the titanium slag product reached 60.68% a variety suitable for the preparation of titanium pigment treatment with concentrated sulfuric acid. Bench-scale testing has shown that more than 95% of TiO_2 It can be washed in slag, and titanium pigment product It was successfully produced containing 99.6% TiO_2 . Production of iron concentrate by one-stage purification Iron to reduce resource losses as much as possible 54.06% Fe grade concentrate was obtained in one step Cleaning in a magnetic field strength of 879 Gs used for the production of blast furnace iron., it can be seen that the overall recovery of high-quality Fe concentrate plus iron concentrate was above 93% and TiO_2 could be regenerated for production in a high-quality concentrate titanium pigment, because the class is acceptable for Iron and steel group.

Conclusion

1. The composition of impurities in the produced raw concentrate is high in ore beneficiation plants. Total Al composition $2O_3$, SiO_2 , MgO and CaO accounted for 11.55%. Mass ratio of $TiO_2/(SiO_2+Al_2O_3+CaO+MgO+TiO_2)$ was 0.58. The

complex use of titanium and iron by reducing - the dilution process from this raw concentrate can be difficult.

2. After the upgrade process with good polishing and two-step low-density magnetic cleaning, high quality vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate was obtained. Total Al composition $2O_3$, SiO_2 , MgO and CaO decreased to 7.73%. The mass ratio of $TiO_2 / (SiO_2 + Al_2O_3 + CaO + MgO + TiO_2)$ was 0.63, This makes the concentrate suitable for production titanium slag.

3. Process mineralogy of high quality vanadium titanomagnetite concentrate showed this main gangue minerals such as sphene, spinel, and pyrope were fine distributed in titanomagnetite particles and their removal would be enormous with physical mineral processing methods difficult

4. In practice, the upgrade process could be done directly to treat the crude concentrate without changing the original process. Fine grinding up to 85% -45 μm is carried out using IsaMill or Tower milling technology and a magnetic drum separator or magnetic separation column can be used obtaining high-quality concentrate and iron concentrate. To recover the ilmenite, the tailings must be enriched. Although the mentioned process involves some capital increases costs and operating costs, most of the TiO_2 in high quality concentrate is obtained and used to produce titanium pigment. Due to the large resource and high value of titanium dioxide, which adds significantly value. Thus, this technique uses cost-effective methods and flexible enough layout for comprehensive using vanadium titanomagnetite. A technology for improving the quality of titanomagnetite concentrate has been proposed, which consists in dividing the ore or the intermediate product of the beneficiation scheme into two technological grades, "rich" and "poor", with subsequent crushing and separate beneficiation of these grades. departments. According to such a technological scheme, ore is divided into easy-rich and difficult-to-process varieties, not at the stages of technological preparation for mining, transportation and crushing, but at the enrichment stage. The advantage of the modernized technology is the relative simplicity of production, since the technological scheme of ore processing changes only in the concentration plant. Under laboratory conditions, an iron-vanadium concentrate containing 63.3% Fe and 0.6% V_2O_5 was obtained. For comparison, in iron-vanadium concentrates produced by current agglomeration and granulation methods of Tebin Bulaq mine, the mass fraction of iron was 60% and 63%, respectively, and vanadium pentoxide was 0.77-0.3%.

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